

Entangled Ethnographies on Alevism in Turkey and Beyond

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Abstract

This special issue maps the processes of consolidation of Alevi Studies as an internationally recognized interdisciplinary field. Firstly, it unpacks the political, institutional, and civil society dynamics that have shaped its development from the 1980s onwards. It argues that the field's consolidation was driven by four interrelated dynamics: political transformation, social visibility, institutional expansion, and the growth of Alevi civil society across Turkey and the European diaspora. Secondly, it illustrates that the paradigm of religious freedom that shaped these political dynamics also dominated the frameworks of early knowledge production, directing scholarly attention toward questions of institutional recognition, legal status, and political representation while sidelining the lived religion perspective. Thirdly, it surveys the scholarly institutions and situates itself within the genealogy of collaborative knowledge production on Alevism. Its distinct contribution lies in its emphasis on ethnographic methodology which expands the research focus on Alevism with specific attention towards everyday practices, material worlds, and communal experiences. The introduction proposes the framework of "entangled ethnographies" as a relational and translocal analytical orientation that foregrounds the interconnectedness of Alevi communities across Turkey and its diasporas. Rather than treating Alevism as a bounded object fixed within a national or territorial frame, "entangled ethnographies" approaches it as a field co-constituted through histories of state violence, migration, institutionalisation, collective memory and ritual practices. The ten contributions assembled in this issue cover a geographical arc stretching from Anatolia to Europe, with particular focus on the material, spatial, and affective dimensions of Alevi life that earlier scholarship has left comparatively underexplored.

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The Emergence of a Scholarly Field: Alevi Studies

As the first quarter of the twenty-first century has come to an end, Alevi Studies now stands before us as an internationally recognized, interdisciplinary field of scholarship that has produced a substantial and growing body of literature, carving out its epistemological contours and mainstream lines of debate which have increasingly become visible. This special issue approaches that consolidated field through a relational and translocal analytical framework that we call “entangled ethnographies”. As we detail in the last section, our aim is to foreground the interconnectedness of Alevi communities across diverse geographical, political, and cultural contexts, particularly between Turkey and its diasporas.

Before the 1990s in Turkey, the field was shaped largely by a limited body of studies that remained silent within the orbit of dominant historical, political, and cultural narratives that had prevailed for nearly a century. Nevertheless, the emergence of this particular field of Alevi studies was not driven by scholarly curiosity alone but shaped by two conjunctural factors. Firstly, the struggle for recognition as equal citizens gradually developed after the coup d'état of 12 September 1980, and secondly, state-sponsored violence directed against that very demand in the 1990s. The publication of *the Alevi Manifesto* in the *Cumhuriyet* newspaper in 1990 marked a foundational moment of collective self-articulation, signalling the beginning of organised Alevi political visibility in Turkey. This was followed by a series of acts of state violence that have since become main reference points for Alevi collective identity and political consciousness: the Sivas Massacre of 1993, in which thirty-three Alevi intellectuals and artists were murdered in an arson attack during a cultural festival; the forced displacement, civilian deaths, and systematic depopulation of Kurdish Alevi communities in Dersim carried out under the “war on terror” policies of 1994; and the armed attacks on the working-class Alevi neighborhoods of Gazi and Ümraniye in Istanbul in 1995.

These events, widely covered in both Turkish and international media, catalysed a new urgency in scholarly engagement with questions of Alevi collective identity, recognition, and political precarity within the Turkish state and society. The initiation of Turkey’s EU accession process in 1999 also embedded Alevism within frameworks of minority rights, religious freedom, and democratic reform and drew sustained institutional and comparative academic attention to the field. From the late 1990s onwards, this political momentum began to generate its own scholarly responses, and the conditions for a more sustained academic engagement with Alevism gradually fell into place. During the 2000s, this process gained further momentum through the fluctuating but sustained visibility of the Alevi movement in the context of Turkey–EU relations, the internationalisation of Alevi demands, and the gradual recognition of Alevis in several European countries as a distinct religious minority with attendant institutional rights.

Although such recognition has remained absent in Turkey, these legal and institutional developments in Europe generated new questions, comparative perspectives, and institutional opportunities for academic research (Coşan Eke et al, 2025). On the one hand, the growth of Alevi Studies and the transnational consolidation of Alevi political and civil-society infrastructures have developed in a mutually reinforcing relationship. On the other hand, this

consolidation has itself been shaped by intersecting, contending and competing political, ethnic, theological, and methodological orientations.

From Political Struggles to Scholarly Foundations

This complexity is in part a reflection of the field's own formation, which remained deeply entangled with the political, ethnic, and theological tensions that have defined Alevi public life more broadly. Alevi Studies emerged not as a unified scholarly project but as a gradually consolidating space of inquiry, shaped by dispersed institutional developments across Turkey, Europe, and, increasingly, transatlantic academic contexts. In its earlier phases, this scholarship took the form of edited volumes and thematic journal issues, which brought together previously scattered contributions under shared analytical frameworks. Over time, these collective efforts gave way to more autonomous institutional expressions of a field: dedicated journals, research centres, scholarly associations, digital platforms, and university-based initiatives. Yet this institutional architecture constitutes only one layer in the formation of a field. There are no universally fixed criteria for defining an area of study, and such definitions frequently vary not only between universities but even across programs within the same institution.

Importantly, fields in their earlier phases of development are often characterized by ongoing disagreements regarding what counts as new knowledge, which methods are appropriate for inquiry, what constitutes acceptable evidence, and which problems deserve scholarly attention. Yet the emergence of a scholarly field did not imply intellectual consensus. The consolidation of Alevi Studies was accompanied by persistent debates concerning methodology, historical interpretation, political representation, and the very definition of Alevism itself. More than two decades ago, Hamit Bozarslan (2003) offered one of the earliest critical assessments of emerging literature in what we today call “Alevi Studies”. His intervention warned against the reproduction of what he called the “myths of research”, the essentialized assumptions that are considered as foundational for the research on Alevism; ahistorical opposition to the Ottoman state, natural alliance with Kemalism, and an inherent affinity with secularism, democracy, and leftist politics. Around the same time, *Kırkbudak: Anadolu Halk İnançları Araştırmaları Dergisi* (2005–2007), the first peer-reviewed journal dedicated to the interdisciplinary study of Alevi belief and practice, provided a more disciplined platform for scholarly engagement with Alevism.

The central claim we advance here is that Alevi Studies has moved decisively beyond this early stage since the 2000s. This special issue, together with the body of collective work listed at the end of the article, should therefore be understood, not merely as a contribution to an emerging field, but as part of the broader consolidation and methodological diversification that now characterizes Alevi Studies. The framework of “entangled ethnographies” we propose here takes these political and historical questions as its starting point, reworking them through attention to situated practice, materiality, and translocal formations.

Dynamics of Consolidation in Alevi Studies

We argue that four interrelated dynamics drove the development of Alevi Studies as a field: political transformation, social visibility, institutional consolidation, and the growth of Alevi civil society. The emergence of the “Alevi question” and its subsequent articulation as the “Alevi Açılımı” (Alevi Opening) at the state level during the 2000s needs to be situated within the broader context of the Alevi Revival. Beginning in the late 1980s, what scholars have termed the Revival involves processes marked by the increasing public visibility of Alevism, growing interest among younger generations in Alevi traditions and collective memory, and renewed engagement with Alevi historical and religious heritage. The launching of the Alevi Opening by the AKP government in 2009 simultaneously responded to and accelerated this ongoing process by placing Alevism on the national political agenda. This generated a new wave of scholarly curiosity for Alevi history, doctrine, practice, and new forms of political organization and activism.

Secondly, due to systematic policies of marginalization and persecution, Alevism, for centuries, had largely been transmitted through oral traditions, embodied ritual practice, and forms of communal knowledge often shielded from the outside world. Beginning in the late twentieth century, however, Alevism increasingly entered the sphere of public discourse through publications, associations, cultural production, media representation, and the public performance of ritual and identity. This transition from relatively esoteric and internally transmitted forms of knowledge to broader public visibility fundamentally transformed Alevism into a new and complex object of academic inquiry. Such a transformation necessitated multidisciplinary approaches capable of engaging simultaneously with theology, history, anthropology, sociology, political science, media studies, and cultural studies.

Thirdly, perhaps most significantly for the present argument, the institutional infrastructure of contemporary Alevi scholarship expanded substantially during the 2000s. Many research centres and institutes devoted to Alevi-related research in Turkey were established during the AKP era, often in ways that intersected with broader state policies concerning Alevism and religious pluralism. This raised questions about the degree to which state-sponsored agendas framed the frameworks of scholarly inquiry. At the same time, contemporary Alevi Studies moved beyond earlier institutionally and theologically centred agendas, increasingly developing as a field concerned with lived practice, migration, memory, music, media, gender, political subjectivity, and transnational forms of community-making. Importantly, a considerable portion of current scholarship is also being produced by researchers with diaspora backgrounds, whose transnational perspectives have significantly reshaped the field’s analytical horizons.

Fourthly, and closely interwoven with the preceding dynamics, the emergence of an organized Alevi civil society infrastructure has played an indispensable, and often underappreciated, role in the consolidation of Alevi Studies. The associations, federations, cultural centres, and foundations that proliferated across Turkey and the European diaspora from the late 1980s onwards did not merely support scholarly work, but they created the very conditions that made it possible. Concretely, since the early 1990s, Alevi organisations in Europe and Turkey have undertaken various activities in different forms to increase the visibility of Alevism, ranging from festivals and concerts aimed at promoting Alevi culture, panel discussions on the definition and current issues of Alevism, and publications of journals and books to

document these discussions, to workshops and political campaigns related to Alevi demands (Zirh, 2008). In many cases, these activities were organised in close dialogue with scholars working on Alevism, who were regularly invited to panels, conferences, workshops, commemorative events, and institutional publications, thereby creating a sustained interface between Alevi activism and academic knowledge production. Collectively, these organizational efforts transformed the focus of the scholarly effort from an object of “negative definition” (Sökefeld, 2008), by which he means a framework defined primarily by its difference from Sunni Islam rather than by its own terms, towards a substantive engagement with Alevi religiosity, history, and community life. Although these processes also generated new tensions concerning representation, authority, and competing interpretations of Alevism within both academic and community contexts, they also shaped the frameworks through which Alevism became intelligible to European academic audiences.

The political and diasporic dynamics traced above ultimately gave rise to a field whose current directions can no longer be contained within the frameworks that first animated it and cannot be defined primarily by questions of recognition, identity politics, or institutional transformation. The field has turned towards what is left underexplored: intersecting formations of gender, class, and race in structuring Alevi religious subjectivity and political mobilization, lived and material religion, sacred geographies, environmental struggles, sensory and affective dimensions of Alevi practice as well as the intergenerational negotiations of identity among third-generation Alevis in Europe. These emerging directions take earlier debates as their starting point and shift the attention toward everyday practices, embodied memory, material sites, and ecological imaginaries across transregional settings. Since these dynamics unfolded simultaneously across Turkey and the European diaspora, rather than within a single national frame, the research in this field demands an analytical framework capable of reflecting on the relational and translocal developments that we highlight through the term “entangled ethnographies”.

Institutional Infrastructure of Knowledge Production on Alevism

The establishment of academic programs at European universities is among the most concrete outcomes of Alevi communities' struggles for recognition in diasporic contexts. While the list of institutions is growing rapidly, the Institute of Alevi Theology at the University of Hamburg (Germany, 2024) and the Alevi Theological Studies at the University of Vienna (Austria, 2018) are the main examples of academic establishments reflecting the professionalization and the recognition gained in Europe. Simultaneously, academy-based institutional initiatives such as the online *Alevi Encyclopedia*, *Alevitisches Archiv: Ethnohistory of Alevi Communities in Anatolia, 16th–20th Century* (Leipzig University, Germany), and *Alevi-Bektashi Digital Archive* (ABDA, USA) have recently emerged as major digital platforms that collect, archive, and preserve the historical and ethnographic sources of Alevi religiosity. (The list of institutions can be found at the end of the article. The Alevi Studies Network also offers a continuously updated overview of this list)

The founding of the *Alevi Studies Network* in 2022 has been a milestone in the process of gathering the field's scholarly community, fostering the circulation and exchange of scholarly

work as well as related artistic and political content. The Network made visible a dispersed yet already interrelated community of MA and PhD researchers, postdoctoral scholars, established academics and independent researchers, Alevi theology departments, and community-based academic initiatives (Gültekin 2026, 21-23). The biennial *Alevi Studies Conference*, initiated at the University of Westminster (London), has fostered interdisciplinary academic collaboration. Academic initiatives within Alevi institutions such as *Rıza Şehri Akademisi* (Dortmund, Germany), *GADEV Alevi Akademisi* (*Garip Dede Dergahı Vakfı*, İstanbul, Turkey) are among the institutions where scholars come together with Alevi communities through lectures, panels, workshops, and public seminars. Since the 2010s, a parallel state-sponsored process of institutionalization has emerged in Turkey and most recently, been consolidated through the *Alevi-Bektaşî Kültür ve Cemevi Başkanlığı* under the Turkish Ministry of Culture and Tourism. This marks a significant moment in which Alevism became an object of state-led knowledge production that appropriates the documentary, archival, and heritage frameworks pioneered by community and academy-based institutions.

Over the past three decades, the growing number of collective publications, edited volumes, and peer-reviewed special issues has also played a decisive role in charting the development of Alevi Studies across languages, disciplines, and thematic orientations. Two edited volumes mark different moments in this collective formation. *Alevi Identity: Cultural, Religious and Social Perspectives* (Olsson et al, 1999), was among the first collective international efforts to situate Alevism within comparative and interdisciplinary scholarly conversation. The edited volume *Kurdish Alevis and the Case of Dersim: Historical and Contemporary Insights* (Gezik and Gültekin 2019) that came a decade later reflects the specialized attention to the process of racialization and foregrounds Kurdish Alevism and Dersim as a distinct historical, sociological, and religious formation within broader Alevi Studies. The present special issue stands within this collective tradition and seeks to extend the methodological and thematic horizons established by earlier collaborative work. Taken together, these collective efforts point to a broader shift from scattered individual contributions toward a multilingual and collectively produced scholarly field. This emerging infrastructure is relational as much as it is cumulative. A comprehensive list of collaborative publications, online archive projects, peer-reviewed periodicals, and special issues is provided at the end of the article.

New Research Horizons in Alevi Studies

As a field, Alevi Studies is in close dialogue with Turkish and Kurdish Studies, while drawing on broader frameworks of Religious Studies, Middle Eastern Studies, Islamic Studies, and diaspora studies. The steadily expanding body of collective scholarly work produced between 1997 and 2025 (see full list below) attests to a field that has gradually carved out a distinctive scholarly identity. It addresses the historical, cultural, religious, political, and sociological dimensions of Alevi communities in Turkey and beyond, with particular attention to questions of identity, recognition, memory, ritual practice, and political mobilization. In doing so, Alevi Studies does not merely function as a sub-field that supplements Turkish or Kurdish Studies as a *corrective addendum*; rather, it actively challenges and reconfigures dominant narratives of Turkish modernity, nationhood, and secularism. In foregrounding the historical experiences, ritual worlds, and political struggles of one of Turkey's largest minoritized

communities Alevi Studies contributes not only to a more nuanced understanding of the region. More significantly, it also leads to a broader rethinking of how categories such as religion, identity, and citizenship are theorized within the social sciences and humanities.

Yet, despite this growing body of scholarship, a substantial portion of the academic literature on Alevism continues to revolve around a relatively limited set of conceptual pathways. The language of religious freedom through which Alevi demands have been articulated privileged certain forms of knowledge production about Alevism, centred on institutional recognition, legal status, and political representation. In doing so, it precluded a lived religion perspective, sidelining attention to everyday practice, ritual life, and communal experience that did not translate into the legal and generic terminology of recognition (Walton & Ilengiz 2024). Issues of recognition, identity politics, representation, institutionalization, migration, and modernity thus remained among the field's dominant axes of inquiry, and scholarly debate became organized through a set of familiar binaries: tradition and modernity, rural and urban, centre and periphery, orthodoxy and heterodoxy, authenticity and transformation. Like any established field, Alevi Studies has developed its own processes of narrative consolidation, where certain questions receive disproportionate attention. For instance, while debates over the ethnic origins of Alevism have been widely analyzed, regional variations in belief and practice, the everyday, affective, and cosmological dimensions of Alevi life remain comparatively underexplored. It took considerably longer for scholarship to turn toward the forms of everyday practice that fell outside the recognition paradigm.

In this sense, prevailing analytical frameworks have tended to privilege institutional authority and public discourse at the expense of more embodied and lived dimensions of religious practice. Consequently, contemporary Alevism has often been narrated through the lens of rupture, loss, and identity crisis, even though Alevi communities continue to generate new forms of continuity, adaptation, and religious creativity under changing socio-political conditions. This special issue proposes the framework of “entangled ethnographies” in direct response to these limitations as a way of rethinking some of the field’s foundational historical, political, and cultural narratives.

Entangled Ethnographies: A Relational Analytical Framework

This special issue takes “entangled ethnographies” to mean not simply multi-sited fieldwork (Marcus 1995) or transnational comparison, but a more ambitious analytical and epistemological intervention in Alevi Studies. The term foregrounds the interconnectedness of Alevi communities across diverse geographical, political, and cultural contexts, particularly between Turkey and its diasporas. It conceptualizes Alevism as a translocal and relational field co-constituted through histories of state violence and state formation, migration, institutionalisation, memory, ritual practice, and everyday life across multiple spatial and temporal transnational scales (Vertovec 2009), rather than as a “bounded object” (Gupta & Ferguson 1992) fixed within single territorial frame. Refuting the naturalized equation between culture, identity and territory, Alevism is approached here not as a phenomenon contained within a single national context (Wimmer & Schiller 2002), nor as a fixed religious tradition merely transported across borders: it is considered as a historically situated and geographically mobile field with migration remaining one of its defining structural conditions.

In this sense, ethnography is approached not merely as a methodological tool for documenting social reality, but as a mode of rethinking the very categories (Marcus & Fischer 1990) through which Alevism has been described, classified, and analysed. Rather than functioning as a purely descriptive framework, “entangled ethnographies” proposes a conceptual and analytical orientation through which Alevism can be reconsidered as a domain shaped by intersecting histories, spatial formations, and diverse forms of material religion. The distinct contribution of ethnographic research, grounded in participant observation and fieldwork, is to move beyond established scholarly dichotomies and engage more closely with the lived, contested, and emergent realities of Alevi life: its affective textures, internal variations, and ongoing transformations. In doing so, the contributors challenge representations of Alevism that reduce it to a fixed religious identity, a cultural residue, or a political category, revealing instead a far more layered terrain in which lived religion, spatial practice, memory, embodiment, and social struggle remain deeply intertwined. These connections across transnational sites and contexts are not smooth or frictionless but are produced through uneven encounters, the processes of racialization, political conflict and struggles (Tsing 2005).

The framework’s analytical contribution lies in the sustained attention the contributors give to the material and spatial dimensions of Alevism. It encompasses sacred places, ritual performances, commemorative forms, affective attachments and the negotiation of religious authority through everyday engagements with landscapes, objects, bodies, and non-human entities. Across different Alevi contexts, they illustrate that religious identity and belonging are not merely articulated through discourses but materialised in place-making practices shaped by intersecting histories, spatial formations, and diverse forms of material religion that actively participate in the production, transformation, and transmission of religious and social life. The framework of “entangled ethnographies” thus invites critical re-examinations of the methodological and epistemological assumptions that have long structured the field, and welcomes novel ways of thinking about comparison, scale, and relationality within Alevi Studies.

Grounded in first-hand ethnographic research conducted across a geographical arc stretching from Anatolia to Europe, the ten contributions introduced below seek not merely to add new case studies but to rethink some of the field's foundational narratives. Several contributions turn to migration and diaspora showing how new spatial configurations have opened up negotiations of memory, belonging, visibility, and afterlife. The ritual spaces and commemorative practices emerging in diasporic settings make clear that Alevism is not transported intact but continuously remade through practices rooted in multiple places. Taken together, the contributions listed below point toward a framework capable of grasping the dynamic interplay of mobility, place-making, collective memory, and lived religion across Turkey and beyond.

Aslı Güçin’s article, [*The Right to Exist as the Foundation of Equal Citizenship: An Ontological Inquiry of State–Citizen Relations in Türkiye*](#), draws on fieldwork in Dersim to rethink Alevi claims for recognition by shifting the analytical focus from legal status to the

ontological conditions of existence within the Turkish state. Rather than approaching the Cemevi debate solely as a matter of institutional inclusion, the study demonstrates how Alevi demands are rooted in a deeper struggle to have their mode of existence acknowledged as legitimate. In doing so, the article fundamentally reframes citizenship as an ontological question and expands discussions of recognition beyond juridical and political categories.

Hayal Hanoğlu's article, [*Alevi Spatial Politics: Placemaking and the Negotiation of Visibility Across Diaspora and Homeland*](#), based on multisided fieldwork in London and Maraş, examines how Alevi communities actively produce and negotiate space as a means of articulating visibility, belonging, and political presence in both homeland and diasporic contexts. Through its focus on placemaking practices, the study demonstrates that space is not a passive backdrop but a contested and relational field shaped by historical marginalisation and contemporary strategies of recognition.

Sinibaldo De Rosa's article, [*Staging the Semahs: Performing Aleviness in Turkey and Europe*](#), grounded in multi-sited ethnography conducted in Turkey, the United Kingdom, and Europe, explores the staged performance of semah rituals as a key site through which Alevi identity is translated, negotiated, and rendered legible across different socio-political contexts. By analysing performances in both Turkey and Europe, the article highlights the entangled relationship between ritual, authenticity, representation, and visibility.

Fabio Salomoni's article, [*Ethnography of the Madımak Massacre Commemorations in Sivas: Changing Narratives, Collective Identities, and Fragmentation*](#) provides a longitudinal ethnography of the Madımak commemorations, tracing their transformation from fragmented secular-left memorial practices into increasingly Alevi-centred rituals of collective identity. Through its analysis of changing narratives, spatial arrangements, and performative forms, the study demonstrates how commemorations function as key sites for the production, negotiation, and transmission of collective memory, while also revealing the growing pluralisation and fragmentation of remembrance.

Bilge Deniz Çatak's article, [*'Only the Body Dies, Souls Can Never Be Slain': Beliefs and Rituals Regarding Death in Alevism*](#) examines Alevi beliefs and ritual practices surrounding death through ethnographic engagement with dedes. Focusing on concepts such as *devriye* and the continuity of the soul, the article demonstrates how funerary practices and understandings of the afterlife are embedded within broader moral and ontological frameworks. At the same time, it traces how these practices are being reshaped under conditions of migration, urbanisation, and changing authority structures.

Meral Salman Yıkılmış's article, [*The Ethnography of the Oblivion of the Traditional Alevi-Tahtacı Belief in Narlıdere*](#) offers an ethnography of disappearance by tracing the dissolution of the Yanyatır Ocak and the resulting erosion of Alevi-Tahtacı religious knowledge in Narlıdere. Based on extensive fieldwork, the article shows how sedentarisation, urbanisation, and the weakening of dede–talip relations have contributed not only to institutional transformation but also to the gradual loss of ritual practices and esoteric knowledge. By foregrounding oblivion as an ethnographic object, the study expands the scope of Alevi Studies beyond narratives of continuity and revival.

Özlem Atik's article, [*Laughing Through Silence: Humour, Language and Memory in Dersim Narratives*](#) examines humour as an affective and narrative medium through which Dersim Alevis engage with collective memory, trauma, and cultural identity. Through ethnographic fieldwork, the article demonstrates how storytelling practices, particularly through Kirmanckî and code-switching, create alternative spaces for remembering and reinterpreting the past across generations. Humour emerges simultaneously as a mode of coping, critique, and cultural continuity.

Ozan Doğan's article, '[*Can a Çingene Be an Alevi?': The Case of Roma from Uşak*](#) brings into focus a largely neglected intersection between Roma Studies and Alevi Studies by examining the religious lives and marginalised positions of Alevi Roma communities in Uşak. Drawing on ethnographic interviews and observations, the article reveals how Roma Alevis experience multilayered forms of exclusion—not only from wider non-Alevi society but also within Roma and Alevi contexts themselves. In doing so, the study foregrounds internal boundary-making, stigma, and contested belonging.

Ümit Çetin and Celia Jenkins' article, [*Decolonial Entangled Ethnographic Research: Transformative Collaborations with the UK Alevi Community Over the Last 15 Years*](#) offers a reflexive account of long-term collaborative engagement with the UK Alevi community, conceptualised as a form of “decolonial entangled ethnography” grounded in activism, co-production, and social justice. Rather than treating ethnography as a detached methodological exercise, the article foregrounds sustained engagement, reciprocity, critical reflexivity, and transformative praxis as key principles for researching marginalised communities.

Finally, Halil Can's article, [*In-/Out-/Transsiders of Transnational Migration: Alevi Families, Belongings and Being in Motion and Transformation from Diasporic Grandchildren's Perspective*](#) examines multi-generational Alevi family trajectories across Turkey and Germany through long-term multi-sited ethnography, with particular attention to the diasporic grandchild generation. By analysing intersecting Alevi, linguistic, and socio-political experiences, the article introduces the concept of “transsider” positionality to capture the in-between spaces of belonging, movement, and transformation that shape diasporic Alevi subjectivities.

The contributions in this special issue suggest the need for a broader reorientation in the study of Alevism. Rather than reproducing established frameworks centred primarily on identity politics, institutions, and political recognition, the special issue points toward an approach that foregrounds entanglement, materiality, mobility, and everyday practice. In doing so, it opens new avenues for understanding Alevism not as a bounded or static object, but as a dynamic and relational field shaped by ongoing interactions between people, places, histories, memories, and non-human actors. These contributions also bear the mark of the particular conditions under which Alevi Studies has developed, where scholarly knowledge has grown in sustained dialogue with community actors, activist networks, and institutional initiatives across Turkey and the diaspora. In this sense, the entanglement the framework names is not only analytical but also reflects the conditions under which this scholarship was produced, in proximity to and often in dialogue with the communities it seeks to understand. This special

issue offers not only a stocktaking of where Alevi Studies stands today, but as an active, ethnographically grounded intervention in shaping where the field is headed.

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Appendix: Selected Institutional Developments in Alevi Studies

(1) The list of Contemporary Actors in Shaping the Alevi Studies' Scholarly Infrastructure

Digital Archive Projects

- [Alevi Encyclopedia \(ISIL code: DE-4607\), Germany \(2025\)](#)
- [Alevitisches Archiv: Ethnohistory of Alevi Communities in Anatolia, 16th–20th Century, Leipzig University, Germany \(2026\)](#)
- Alevi-Bektashi Digital Archive (ABDA), USA
- [Catalogue of the Alevi-Bektashi Cultural Institute \(ABK\)](#)

University Programs (Turkey & Europe)

In Europe

- [Institute of Alevi Theology, Hamburg, Germany \(2024\)](#)
- [Alevi Theological Studies, University of Vienna, Austria \(2018\)](#)
- [Institut Alevitische Religion, Kirchliche Pädagogische Hochschule Vienna/Krems, Austria \(2015\)](#)
- [Alevi Theology, Weingarten, Germany \(2014\)](#)

In Turkey

- [İnönü Üniversitesi Alevilik Araştırmaları Enstitüsü \(2018\)](#)
- [Toros Üniversitesi, Alevilik-Bektaşılık Uygulama ve Araştırma Merkezi \(2015\)](#)
- Hitit Üniversitesi, Hacı Bektaş Veli Araştırma ve Uygulama Merkezi (2015)
- [Nevşehir Hacı Bektaş Veli Üniversitesi, Hacı Bektaş Veli Araştırma ve Uygulama Enstitüsü \(2014\)](#)
- [Munzur Üniversitesi, Alevilik Araştırma ve Uygulama Merkezi \(2011\)](#)
- [Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi, Alevi Bektaşî Kültürü Uygulama ve Araştırma Merkezi \(2011\)](#)

- [Dicle Üniversitesi – Alevilik ve Ehlibeyt Kültürü Uygulama ve Araştırma Merkezi \(2012\)](#)
- [Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi, Türk Kültürü ve Hacı Bektaş Veli Araştırma ve Uygulama Merkezi \(1987\)](#)

Scholarly Networks

- [Biennial Alevi Studies Conference, initiated at the University of Westminster, London \(Since 2023\)](#)
- [Alevi Studies Network \(founded 2022\)](#)

The List of Peer Review Journals

- [Niyaz – Alevilik-Bektaşilik Araştırmaları Dergisi \(since 2025, Turkey\)](#)
- [Edep Erkan Dergisi \(since 2022, Turkey\)](#)
- [Sürek – Alevilik Bektaşilik ve Kültür Araştırmaları Dergisi \(since 2023, Turkey\)](#)
- [Ahmet Yesevi Dergisi \(since 2023, Turkey\)](#)
- [Alevilik-Bektaşilik Araştırmaları Dergisi / Journal of Alevism-Bektashism Studies \(since 2010, Germany\)](#)
- [Türk Kültürü ve Hacı Bektaş Veli Araştırma Dergisi \(since 1994; current title since 2006, Turkey\)](#)
- Alevilik Araştırmaları Dergisi / The Journal of Alevi Studies (2011–2019, Turkey)
- Hünkâr Alevilik Bektaşilik Akademik Araştırmalar Dergisi (2014, Turkey)
- [Kırkbudak – Anadolu Halk İnançları Araştırmaları Dergisi / Journal of Anatolian Folk Beliefs \(2005–2007, Turkey\)](#)

Community-Based Academic Initiatives

- Rıza Şehri Akademisi, Dortmund, Germany
- GADEV Alevi Akademisi (Garip Dede Dergahı Vakfı), Istanbul, Turkey
- Alevi Akademisi, Leimen, Germany
- Alevitische Akademie (Alevi Academy), Vienna, Austria

The Chronology of Edited Volumes (Turkish, English and German)

2026 (*forthcoming*) — *Interdisciplinary Studies on Alevism*. Ed. Coşan Eke, Deniz. Wiesbaden: Springer: Social and Cultural Anthropology Series.

2026 — *Sufism in Ottoman and Post-Ottoman Europe: Entanglements in Past and Present*. Eds. Cem Kara, Evelyn Reuter, and Zsófia Turóczy. Routledge.

2025 — *Alevitentum: Tradition – Theologie – Zukunft – Migration – Identität – Integration / Alevilik: Gelenek – Teoloji – Gelecek – Göç – Kimlik – Entegrasyon*. Eds. Bülent Keleş and Matthias Mertes. Bund Alevitischer Gemeinden e.V.

2025 — *Nazımiye – Tarih, Hafıza ve Alevi Kültürü Üzerine Kapsamlı Bir Derleme*. Eds. Şükrü Aslan, Zülfiye Koçak, and Ali Sağlam. Ankara: Ütopya Yayınevi.

2025 — *Aleviler ve Cumhuriyet*. Ed. Ayhan Yalçınkaya. Ankara: Dipnot Yayınları.

2024 — *Dersim/Tunceli'nin Yüz Yılı: 1900–2000*. Ed. Mesut Özcan. Oroji Yayınları.

2024 — *TBMM'de İlk Alevi Milletvekilleri: Siyaset ve Aleviler*. Ed. Mehmet Ertan. İstanbul: GADEV / GADEV Yayınları.

2024 — *Alevi Topluluklar: Aleviler/Alevilik Saha Araştırmaları Konferansları – I*. Ed. Şükrü Aslan. GADEV Yayınları.

2024 — *Dersim – Identität und Vernichtung*. Eds. Christian Gudehus and Alexander Husenbeth. Gießen: Psychosozial-Verlag.

2024 — *Aleviler: Din, Beden, Cinsiyet, Neşeden Kedere*. Eds. Çilem Küçükkeleş and Ayhan Yalçınkaya. Ankara: Dipnot Yayınları.

2024 — *Sosyal Bilimler Perspektifinden Aleviler ve Alevilik 2*. Eds. Fikriye Yücesoy, Ozan Çavdar, and Şükrü Aslan. Ankara: Ütopya Yayınevi.

2023 — *Alevilerin Dönüşümü: İnanç, Ritüel ve Topluluklar Üzerine Saha Araştırmaları*. Ed. Volkan Ertit. Karahan Kitabevi.

2023 — *Sosyal Bilimler Perspektifinden Alevilik I*. Eds. Şükrü Aslan, Çiğdem Boz, and Cemal Salman. Ankara: Ütopya Yayınevi.

2022 — *The Alevi in Modern Turkey and the Diaspora: Recognition, Mobilisation and Transformation*. Eds. Derya Ozkul and Hege Markussen. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.

2020 — *Aesthetic and Performative Dimensions of Alevi Cultural Heritage*. Eds. Martin Greve, Ulaş Özdemir, and Raoul Motika. Baden-Baden: Ergon Verlag.

2020 — *Aleviler ve Sosyalistler: Bir Karşılaştırmaların Notları*. Eds. Ayhan Yalçınkaya and Halil Karaçalı. Ankara: Dipnot Yayınları.

2018 / 2020 — *Alevism as an Ethno-Religious Identity: Contested Boundaries*. Eds. Celia Jenkins, Suavi Aydın, and Ümit Çetin. London: Routledge.

2019 — *Dersim Üç Dağ İçinde*. Ed. Serhat Halis. Ankara: NotaBene Yayınları.

2019 — *Kurdish Alevi and the Case of Dersim: Historical and Contemporary Insights*. Eds. Erdal Gezik and Ahmet Kerim Gültekin. Lanham: Lexington Books.

2018 / 2019 — *Transmission Processes of Religious Knowledge and Ritual Practice in Alevism: Between Innovation and Reconstruction*. Eds. Johannes Zimmermann, Janina Karolewski, and Robert Langer. Frankfurt am Main et al.: Peter Lang.

2018 — *Alevism Between Standardisation and Plurality: Negotiating Texts, Sources and Cultural Heritage*. Eds. Benjamin Weineck and Johannes Zimmermann. Berlin: Peter Lang.

2017 — *Alevis in Europe: Voices of Migration, Culture and Identity*. Ed. Tözün Issa. New York: Routledge.

2015 — *Kızılbaşlık, Alevilik, Bektaşilik: Tarih-Kimlik-İnanç-Ritüel*. Eds. Yalçın Çakmak and İmran Gürtaş. İstanbul: İletişim Yayınları.

2015 — *Ötekiler'in Peşinde: Ahmet Yaşar Ocak'a Armağan*. Eds. Mehmet Öz and Fatih Yeşil. İstanbul: Timaş Yayınları.

2013 — *“Ocak” und “Dedelik”: Institutionen religiösen Spezialistentums bei den Aleviten*. Eds. Robert Langer, Hüseyin Ağuçınoğlu, and Janina Karolewski. Peter Lang.

2013 — *Dört Dağa Sığmayan Kent: Dersim Üzerine Ekonomi-Politik Yazılar*. Eds. Ş. Gürçağ Tuna and Gözde Orhan. Patika Kitap.

2013 — *Dersim'i Parantezden Çıkarmak: Dersim Sempozyumu'nun Ardından*. Eds. Şükrü Aslan, Songül Aydın, and Zeliha Hepkon. İstanbul: İletişim Yayınları.

2011 — *Aleviten in Deutschland: Grundlagen, Veränderungsprozesse, Perspektiven*. Friedmann Eißler. Berlin: Evangelische Zentralstelle für Weltanschauungsfragen / EZW.

2010 — *Hacı Bektaş Veli: Güneşte Zerresinden, Deryada Katresinden*. Eds. Pınar Ecevitoğlu, Ayhan Yalçınkaya, and Ali Murat İrat. Ankara: Dipnot Yayınları.

2010 — *Herkesin Bildiği Sır: Dersim: Tarih, Toplum, Ekonomi, Dil ve Kültür*. Ed. Şükrü Aslan. İstanbul: İletişim Yayınları.

2008 — *Aleviten in Deutschland: Identitätsprozesse einer Religionsgemeinschaft in der Diaspora*. Ed. Martin Sökefeld. Bielefeld: transcript Verlag.

2005 — *Alevis and Alevism: Transformed Identities*. Ed. Hege Irene Markussen. Istanbul: The Isis Press.

2005 — *Migration und Ritualtransfer: Religiöse Praxis der Aleviten, Jesiden und Nusairier zwischen Vorderem Orient und Westeuropa*. Eds. Robert Langer, Raoul Motika, and Michael Ursinus. Peter Lang.

2003 — *Turkey's Alevi Enigma: A Comprehensive Overview*. Eds. Paul J. White and Joost Jongerden. Leiden/Boston: Brill.

2003 — *Bilgi Toplumunda Alevilik*. Ed. İbrahim Bahadır. Bielefeld: Bielefeld Alevi Kültür Merkezi.

2002 — *Osmanlı ve Cumhuriyet Dönemi Alevi Kültür ve Tarihi*. Ed. İbrahim Bahadır. Bielefeld: Bielefeld Alevi Kültür Merkezi.

1999 — *Alevi Identity: Cultural, Religious and Social Perspectives*. Eds. Tord Olsson, Elisabeth Özdalga, and Catharina Raudvere. Istanbul: Swedish Research Institute in Istanbul.

1995 — *Syncretistic Religious Communities in the Near East: Collected Papers of the International Symposium "Alevism in Turkey and Comparable Syncretistic Religious Communities in the Near East in the Past and Present"*. Eds. Krisztina Kehl-Bodrogi, Barbara Kellner-Heinkele, and Anke Otter-Beaujean. Leiden/New York/Köln: Brill.

Chronology of Special Issues in Peer-Reviewed Journals on Alevi Studies

2026 — Entangled Ethnographies on Alevism in Turkey and Beyond. *Studies in Ethnicity and Nationalism*. Guest editors: Ahmet Kerim Gültekin, Besim Can Zırh, Çiçek İleğiz, and Deniz Coşan-Eke.

2024 — Alevi-Bektashi Studies: New Directions. *Journal of the Ottoman and Turkish Studies Association*, 11 (2). Guest editors: Ayfer Karakaya-Stump and Cemal Kafadar.

2020 — Alevi Kurds: History, Politics and Identity. *Kurdish Studies*, 8 (1). Guest editors: Ümit Çetin, Celia Jenkins, and Suavi Aydın.

2019 — Alevism as an Ethno-Religious Identity: Contested Boundaries. *National Identities*, 20 (1). Guest editors: Celia Jenkins, Suavi Aydın, and Ümit Çetin.